

1 **Antiinflammatory and antioxidant activities from the basolateral**
2 **fraction of Caco-2 cells exposed to a rosmarinic acid enriched extract**

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17 **ABSTRACT**

18 The potential use of *Origanum majorana* L. as a source of bioavailable phenolic
19 compounds, specifically rosmarinic acid (RA), has been evaluated. Phenolic
20 bioavailability was tested using an *in vitro* digestion process followed by a Caco-2
21 cellular model of intestinal absorption. The HPLC-PAD-MS/MS analysis showed the
22 main components in the extract were 6-hydroxyluteolin-7-O-glucoside and rosmarinic
23 acid, followed by luteolin-O-glucoside. After digestion process, the amount of total
24 phenolic compounds (TPC) only decreased slightly, although a remarkable reduction in
25 RA (near 50%) was detected. Bioavailable fraction contained 7.37 ± 1.39 mg/L digested
26 extract of RA with small quantities of lithospermic acid and diosmin and presented an
27 important antioxidant activity (0.89 ± 0.09 mmol Trolox/L digested extract). Besides, this
28 bioavailable fraction produced a significant inhibition in TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6
29 secretion, using a human THP-1 macrophages model. Therefore, RA content in the
30 basolateral compartment could play an important role in the antioxidant and anti-
31 inflammatory activities found.

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33 Key words: anti-inflammatory activity, antioxidant activity, rosmarinic acid, *in vitro*
34 digestion, Caco-2 cells.

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39 INTRODUCTION

40 *Origanum majorana* L. (marjoram) is a culinary herb often used in foods. Its essential
41 oil and extracts have been indicated to possess antioxidant, antimicrobial, anticancer
42 and anti-inflammatory activities.^{1,2} These activities have been attributed to the presence
43 of a high percentage of phenolic acids and flavonoids in marjoram leaves³ particularly,
44 to rosmarinic acid (RA), an ester of caffeic acid and 3,4-dihydroxyphenyllactic acid
45 naturally occurring in marjoram.^{4,5} Antioxidant activity of RA has been generally
46 admitted, since this compound may act as free radical scavenger.^{6,7} Related to RA anti-
47 inflammatory effects, Jiang et al.⁸ showed that this compound down regulated the levels
48 of TNF- α , IL-6 and high mobility box 1 protein in bacterial lipopolysaccharide (LPS)
49 induced RAW264.7 cells, indicating that RA might inhibit activation of the nuclear
50 factor- κ B pathway by inhibiting I κ B kinase activity. Accordingly, Zdarilová et al.⁹
51 reported that RA inhibited LPS-induced up-regulation of IL-1 β , IL-6, TNF- α and
52 suppressed expression of iNOS in human gingival fibroblasts. Further, Lembo et al.¹⁰
53 indicated that RA produced a significant reduction in IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-8 and TNF- α gene
54 expression in HaCat cells after UVB irradiation.

55 In order to extrapolate results founded *in vitro* to *in vivo* situation, it is important to
56 know the bioavailability of bioactive compounds. Therefore, the use of an *in vitro*
57 digestion/Caco-2 cell culture model has been proposed by several authors as an
58 economical and useful alternative to study the bioavailability of these compounds.^{11,12}
59 Thus, although the transepithelial transport of RA in intestinal Caco-2 cells monolayers
60 has been studied,¹³ it is crucial to investigate the effect that plant matrix plays on its
61 bioavailability, since plant material matrix may alter absorption and bioavailability of
62 phytochemicals.¹⁴ For that matter, it would be very interesting to determine the anti-
63 inflammatory and antioxidant effect of the bioavailable fractions of marjoram extracts

64 enriched in RA, in order to corroborate the biological activities described for these
65 extracts.

66

67 Solid –liquid extraction (SLE) is the most traditional technology used to extract active
68 compounds from plant matrix. It is widely known that higher temperatures enhance the
69 solubility of the solute in the solvent and thus improve its recovery. Nevertheless, the
70 SLE temperature is limited by solvent boiling and, in some cases, by the loss of volatile
71 compounds. In this regard, pressurized liquid extraction (PLE) allows the use of
72 solvents in a liquid state at higher temperatures. Furthermore, a compression effect is
73 made on vegetal particles, which also contributes to improve extraction yield; moreover,
74 lower amount of solvent is required, extraction is faster and volatiles loss is
75 minimized.¹⁵ Thus, several studies proposed PLE extraction as an alternative to
76 conventional solid/liquid extraction in order to obtain phenolic compounds from herbs
77 and spices.^{16,17}

78

79 However, it is hard to obtain a highly concentrated extracts in phenolic compounds
80 using only PLE, due to the complexity and the presence of impurities in crude extracts
81 of herbal raw materials. Nowadays, the use of adsorption resins has been proposed as
82 one of the most useful tools for selective enrichment of phenolic compounds from plant
83 material, such as naringenin recovery from orange juice¹⁸ or anthocyanins from
84 grapes.¹⁹

85 For this purpose, some of the most commonly employed resins are XAD-2, XAD-7,
86 XAD-16 and Oasis HLB, that have been successfully used for phenolic compounds
87 enrichment from natural extracts.^{20,21} Among them, XAD-7 has been proposed for
88 rosmarinic acid enrichment from *Lavandula vera*²² or *Rabdosia serra*.²³

89

90 The aim of this work was to study the anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties of
91 the bioavailable fraction of PLE extracts enriched in rosmarinic acid. In order to
92 increase the quantity of RA in PLE extracts of marjoram an amberlite XAD-7HP resin
93 was employed. The bioavailability of both, original and enriched extracts, was
94 determined by using an *in vitro* digestion/Caco-2 cell culture model. Thus, the anti-
95 inflammatory and antioxidant activity of the basolateral fraction was measured.

96

97 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

98 **Chemicals**

99 Ethanol of analytical grade and Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent were obtained from Panreac
100 (Madrid, Spain). (\pm)-6-Hydroxy-2,5,7,8-tetramethylchromane-2-carboxylic acid
101 (Trolox, <97%), 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl free radical (DPPH), gallic acid for
102 titration (<97,5%), and thiazolyl blue tetrazolium bromide (MTT) were purchased from
103 Sigma Aldrich (Madrid, Spain). Formic acid (99%) was obtained from Acros Organics
104 (Madrid, Spain) and acetonitrile HPLC grade from Macron Fine Chemicals (Madrid,
105 Spain). Reference substances (chromatographic purity \geq 95%) for phenolic compounds
106 identification such as cryptochlorogenic acid, neochlorogenic acid and rosmarinic acid
107 were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Madrid, Spain). Apigenin, apigenin 7-O-
108 glururonide, caftaric acid, diosmin, lithospermic acid, luteolin, salvianolic acid and
109 vicenin 2 were from Phytolab (Madrid, Spain). Ethyl gallate, apigenin 7-O-glucoside,
110 caffeic acid, luteolin 7-O- β -D-glucoside, p-coumaric acid and protocatechuic acid were
111 obtained from Extrasynthese S.A. (Genay, France). Finally, luteolin-7-O-B-D-
112 glucuronide were from HWI Analytic GmbH (Rülzheim, Germany). The water used in
113 this study was ultrapure type 1 (Millipore, Madrid, Spain).

114

115 **Marjoram samples and PLE extraction**

116 Marjoram sample consisted of dried leaves obtained from an herbalist shop (Murciana
117 herboristería, Murcia, Spain). The sample was grinded in a knife mill (Grindomix GM
118 200, Retsch, Llanera, Spain) and the particle size was determined by sieving the ground
119 plant material to the appropriate size (<500 µm). The whole sample was stored at -20°C
120 until use.

121 Extractions were carried out in an ASE 350 system from Dionex Corporation
122 (Sunnyvale, CA, USA) equipped with a solvent controller unit. Each extraction cell (11
123 mL of capacity) was filled with a mixture of 1g of solid sample and 4 g of sea sand.
124 Then, the cell was filled with the solvent (a mixture of ethanol: water, 70:30) up to a
125 pressure of 1500 psi and heated to 100°C. Static extractions were performed for 10 min.
126 The extracts were recovered in glass vials, ethanol was eliminated by evaporation and
127 extracts were lyophilized. The dried samples were stored at 4°C in the dark until
128 analysis.

129

130 **Enrichment in phenolic compounds by resin column**

131 Enrichment experiments were carried out in a glass column (3 cm x 50 cm) packed with
132 XAD-7HP resin (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA). In order to remove the
133 monomers and pyrogenic agents trapped inside the pores during the synthesis process, a
134 pre-treatment of this resin was realized following the method described by Lin et al.²³
135 After pre-treatment process, the resin was rehydrated overnight with ethanol at 4°C and
136 packed with a bed volume (BV) of 174 mL. In order to remove the ethanol, a distilled
137 water washing was placed (4BV) at constant flow of 4BV/h. PLE extract was dissolved
138 in acid water (pH 3) (15 mg/mL) and 45 mL was applied onto the column. After

139 absorption equilibrium was reached (1h), the column was washed with 2BV of distilled
140 water and eluted with 3BV of 80% ethanol at a constant flow of 2 BV/h. The eluted
141 fraction was collected, evaporated to remove methanol, freeze-dried and stored at -20°C
142 until evaluation.

143

144 **Determination of total phenolic content (TPC) and antioxidant activity**

145 In order to determine the TPC, Folin-Ciocalteu reagent method was applied as
146 described by Singleton et al.²⁴ The results were expressed as mg of gallic acid
147 equivalents (GAE)/g extract. Antioxidant activity was determined by DPPH method.
148 This method was applied according to Brand-Williams et al.²⁵ protocol. The results were
149 expressed as TEAC value (mmol trolox/g extract or L of digested extract). All analyses
150 were done in triplicate.

151

152 **Chemical characterization of samples**

153 HPLC-PAD analysis of phenolic compounds was performed by using an Agilent HPLC
154 1260 Infinity series system with photodiode-array detector (Agilent Technologies Inc.,
155 Santa Clara, CA, USA). A reverse phase ACE Excell 3 Super C18 column (150 mm x
156 4.6 mm, 3 µm particle size) protected by a guard column ACE 3 C18-AR (10 mm x 3
157 mm) was used at 35°C. 20 µL of sample (extract, digested extract, apical or basolateral
158 fractions) was injected previously filtered by 0.45 µm PVDF filter.

159 Chromatographic separation was achieved using solvent A (99.9/0.1 water/formic acid
160 v/v) and solvent B (ACN) at a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min as follows: 0 min, 0% B; 1 min,
161 0% B; 6 min, 15% B; 21 min, 25% B; 26 min, 35% B; 36 min, 50%; 41 min, 50% B; 44
162 min, 100% B; 49 min, 0% B. Chromatograms were recorded at 280 nm, 320 nm and
163 360 nm. Peaks were tentatively identified according to its retention time and UV-Vis

164 spectrum by comparison with analytical standards. Ethyl gallate was added as internal
165 standard in each analyze sample before it was filtered.

166 Confirmation of the identified compounds was carried out by HPLC-MS analyses.
167 HPLC 1100 (Agilent Technologies Inc., Santa Clara, CA, USA) coupled to a hybrid
168 quadrupole-time of flight mass spectrometer (QTOF, QSTAR pulsar i, ABSciex)
169 equipped with a turbo ion electrospray source was used. MS experiments in negative
170 mode were carried out in TOF/MS and MS/MS mode. The instrumental parameters
171 were set as follows: mass range 50-2000 Da; ion spray voltage (IS) -4500 V; ion source
172 gas pressure (GS1): 65 psi; (GS2): 65psi; curtain gas pressure (Cur): 20 psi;
173 declustering potencial (DP): 30 V; focusing potencial (FP): 210 V; declustering
174 potencial 2 (DP2): 15 V; Collision gas: 3 psi in MS experiments and 5 psi in MSMS
175 experiments. In TOF/MS experiments, just before separation, an external calibration in
176 the mass spectrometer was performe with a mixture of phosphazenes and verified after
177 the assays. The maximum error accepted to calibrate in the whole range of mass was 5
178 ppm. In MSMS product ion experiments, the ion precursor was selected and the
179 collision energy was fixed to 35 eV. Just before each MS/MS experiment, the
180 instrument was calibrated with taurocholic acid and verified after the experiment. The
181 accurate masses obtained were processed using the elemental compositon calculator
182 incorporated in the Analyst Software (Applied Biosystems). A margin of error up to 5
183 ppm for unknown compounds was allowed. Chromatographic conditions were similar
184 as for HPLC-PAD analysis.

185 Quantification of identified compounds was carried out by using calibration curves of
186 its authentic standard (Extrasynthese S.A., Genay, France) at five levels in triplicate by
187 HPLC-PAD. Moreover, 6-hydroxyluteolin-7-O-glucoside, luteolin-O-glucoside,

188 lithospermic acid isomer and salvianolic acid isomer were quantified by the calibration
189 curve of luteolin-7-o-glucoside, lithospermic acid and salvianolic acid, respectively.
190 Validation of the chromatographic method (LOD, LOQ, precision, repeatability,
191 stability and recovery) was previously done (data not shown).

192

193 ***In vitro* digestion**

194 The digestion process was carried out following a previously published protocol¹²
195 slightly modified. Briefly, each extract (100 mg) was dissolved in 5 mL of ethanol:
196 water (50:50), mixed with 0.1 mL α - amylase from human saliva type XIII-A (Sigma-
197 Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) (9.3 mg in Cl_2Ca 1 mM) and shaking for 2 min at 37°C
198 (oral phase). Stomach and intestinal phases were carried out employing a titrator Titrimo
199 Plus 877 (Methrom AG, Herisau, Switzerland). Thus, oral phase was mixed with 25 mL
200 of a gastric solution (127 mg of porcine pepsin from porcine mucosa, 536 U/mg,
201 (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) at pH 2 (adjusted with 0.1M HCL) and shaking
202 for 1h at 37°C. After gastric digestion, samples were adjusted to pH 7 with 1M NaOH
203 prior to the pancreatic step. Next, a pancreatic-bile extract containing 9.3 mg pancreatin
204 (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) and 115.7 mg of bile salts in 2.8 mL of 10mM
205 trizme-maleate buffer was incorporated and incubated for 2h at 37°C. At the end of
206 digestion, the enzyme reaction was stopped immediately by cooling the samples in ice
207 and samples were kept at -20°C until analysis.

208

209 **Caco-2 experiments**

210 Caco-2 cells (American Type Culture Collection (ATCC), Manassas, VA, USA) were
211 maintained in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10%
212 fetal bovine serum (FBS), 100 U/mL penicillin, 100 mg/mL streptomycin, 1%

213 nonessential amino acids and 2 mM L-glutamine (Gibco, Paisley, UK) at 37 °C in at
214 humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂. The cytotoxic effect on Caco-2 cells of the
215 extracts after digestion process was tested using 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-
216 diphenyl tetrazolium bromide (MTT) assay following Mosmann²⁶ method. Briefly,
217 Caco-2 cells were plated in 24-well plates until cell monolayers were obtained. Then the
218 medium was aspirated and cells were treated with different concentrations of digested
219 extracts for 6h. After the medium was removed and cells washed and incubated with
220 MTT for 2-3h. The medium was removed and 500 µL of DMSO were added. The
221 absorbance was measured at 570nm.

222 For transport experiments, Caco-2 cells were seeded onto six-wells Transwell[®] plates
223 (0.4 µm pore size, inserts of 24 mm diameter, Costar, Corning, Madrid, Spain) at a
224 density of 3x10⁵ cells per insert. The cells were maintained along 21 days, once the
225 monolayer was formed, during which time culture medium was replaced every three
226 days. The Caco-2 monolayer was used when transepithelial electrical resistance (TEER)
227 (EVOM2, World Precision Instruments, Hitchin, UK) values were larger than 350 Ω
228 cm². ~~The integrity of the monolayer was checked by measuring the transepithelial~~
229 ~~electrical resistance (TEER) (EVOM2, World Precision Instruments, Hitchin, UK).~~
230 Apical and basolateral compartments were washed once with PBS and then incubated
231 with 1.5 mL and 2.6 mL of supplement DMEM without FBS. 150 µL of digested
232 extracts were incorporate in the apical compartment and incubated for 6 h at 37 °C.
233 TEER value was measured twice before and after experiment to monitor the integrity of
234 the Caco-2 monolayer. Then apical and basolateral samples were freeze-dried and
235 stored at – 20°C prior analysis.

236

237 **Anti-inflammatory activity of basolateral samples from Caco-2 experiments**

238 Human THP-1 monocytes (ATCC, Manassas, VA, USA) were cultured in RPMI 1640
239 culture medium supplemented with 10% FBS, 100 U/mL penicillin, 100 mg/mL
240 streptomycin, 2 mM L-glutamine (Gibco, Paisley, UK) and 0.05 mM β -mercaptoethanol
241 (Sigma-Aldrich, Madrid, Spain) at 37°C in 95% humidified air containing 5% CO₂.
242 Cells were plated at a density of 5×10^5 cells/mL in 24 wells plates. Differentiation of
243 monocytes to macrophages (THP-1/M cells) was induced by maintaining the cells with
244 100 ng/ml of phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA) (Sigma-Aldrich, Madrid, Spain)
245 for 48 h. The viability of THP-1/M cells in presence of basolateral medium from Caco-2
246 experiments was tested used the MTT assay following Mosmann²⁶ method. The assays
247 were performed in triplicate.

248 After differentiation, cells were washed with PBS and incubated with 0.05 μ g/mL of
249 LPS from E. Coli O55:B5 (Sigma-Aldrich, Spain) in presence of the basolateral
250 medium from Caco-2 experiments for 24 h. Then, the supernatant was frozen at -20°C.
251). Positive controls represented THP-1/M cells incubated with LPS but without
252 basolateral medium and negative controls indicated cells non stimulated with LPS and
253 without basolateral medium.

254 The release of TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6 was measured in the supernatants of THP-1/M
255 cells using ELISA kits (BD Biosciences, Aalst, Belgium), according to manufacturer's
256 instructions. The color generated (yellow) was quantified by measuring the optical
257 density at 450 nm with substrate correction at 570 nm using a multiscanner autoreader
258 (InfiniteM200 Tecan, Barcelona, Spain). The results were expressed as the mean of
259 three determinations \pm standard deviation.

260

261 **Statistical analysis**

262 Experimental results are expressed as means \pm standard deviation (SD). One-way
263 analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by least significant difference test was used at
264 $p \leq 0.05$ to look for differences between means. Statistical analyses were performed
265 using Statgraphics v. Centurion XVI software for Windows (Statpoint Inc., Warrenton,
266 VA, USA).

267

268 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

269 **Phenolic and functional characterization of PLE and enriched extracts**

270 PLE extracts from marjoram were carried out using 70% ethanol, 100°C and 10 min.
271 These extraction conditions were supported by previous studies (data not shown)
272 developed to obtain extracts with a high content of TPC and an important antioxidant
273 activity. The PLE obtained extract presented a TPC of 265.9 mg GAE/g extract and a
274 TEAC value of 1.81 mmol Trolox/g extract.

275 For the purpose to achieve extract enrichment in phenolic compounds, XAD-7HP resin
276 was used. The effectiveness of this kind of resins for rosmarinic acid enrichment has
277 been previously reported.²³ As Table 1 shows, the use of this resin achieved a TPC 1.5-
278 fold superior to the original PLE extract. ~~representing a 39% of the extract.~~ Thus, the
279 amount of phenolic compounds presented in the new extract represented a 39% of total
280 extract. Moreover, this enriched extract also presented significantly higher antioxidant
281 activity (Table 1).

282 The HPLC-PAD-MS-QTOF analysis of the phenolic compounds (Table 2) resulted in
283 the identification of 17 compounds in the extracts (original and enriched), whereas p-
284 coumaric and neochlorogenic acids were also identified in the digested extracts. All the
285 identified compounds in the extracts had been previously described in marjoram
286 extracts (Kawabata et al., 2003; Taamalli et al, 2015; Vallverdú-Queralt et al., 2015).

287 Moreover, according to its specific λ_{\max} , accurate mass and MS/MS fragments 6-
288 hydroxyluteolin-7-O-glucoside, luteolin-O-glucoside, lithospermic acid isomer and
289 salvianolic acid isomer were tentatively identified in the extracts (de Beer et al., 2011;
290 Greenham et al., 2003; Taamalli et al., 2015).

291 Both extracts showed a similar qualitative composition, although important quantitative
292 differences were found (Table 3). Therefore, enriched extract presented, in general, an
293 increase between 1.8-1.5 times in the quantity of all compounds in relation to the
294 original extract. Accordingly, the main components in both extracts were 6-
295 hydroxyluteolin-7-O-glucoside and rosmarinic acid, followed by a luteolin-O-glucoside
296 and an isomer of salvianolic acid.

297 This phenolic composition was consistent with other research works where marjoram
298 extracts had been characterized by an extended composition in phenolic acids and
299 flavonoids. These works reported that, among phenolic acids, RA was the main
300 compound detected. In addition, luteolin and its glucosil derivatives have been also
301 detected as the main flavonoids.^{3,16}

302

303 **Phenolic composition and antioxidant activity of the extracts during *in vitro*** 304 **digestion**

305 Digestion effect in TPC and antioxidant activity for both extracts is shown in Table 1.
306 After digestion process, the amount of TPC only decreased slightly for both extracts, as
307 well as antioxidant activity. Notwithstanding, digestion step produced a remarkable
308 reduction of RA (approx. 50%) in both original and enriched extracts (Table 3). This
309 decrease in RA content during gastrointestinal digestion was in agreement with other
310 studies that reported RA degradation or transformation into other compounds during *in*
311 *vitro* gastrointestinal digestion.^{27,28} Moreover, Zoric et al.²⁹ showed that gastrointestinal

312 stability of RA was highly influenced by plant matrix, indicating that the presence of
313 some flavonoids such as luteolin or apigenin enhances the stability rate of RA during
314 digestion process.

315

316 ~~On the other hand~~ Moreover, the quantitative analysis of phenolic composition after the
317 digestion process (Table 3) showed that most compounds, presented in both extracts,
318 were affected by digestion step to a lesser or greater extent. For that matter, although
319 RA was reduced after digestion, it represented the main compound in both digested
320 extracts, followed by luteolin 7-O-glucoside, 6-hydroxyluteolin-7-O-glucoside and
321 luteolin-O-glucoside. Among these compounds, 6-hydroxyluteolin-7-O-glucoside and
322 luteolin-O-glucoside were most affected by the digestion step, meanwhile, luteolin 7-O-
323 glucoside and glucuronide, were much less affected, even more apigenin 7-O-glucoside
324 and glucuronide increased after digestion. It should be also noted the appearance of
325 neochlorogenic and p-coumaric acids in both digested extracts, compounds not detected
326 in the non-digested extracts, and whose presence could be attributed to isomerization
327 and degradation processes of initial phenolic acids. Accordingly, Xie et al.³⁰ noted
328 isomeric transformations of chlorogenic acids, where cryptochlorogenic acid was
329 mainly turned into chlorogenic acid at pH 7 and 37 °C, in agreement with intestinal
330 conditions. Moreover, some studies have shown the presence of coumaric acid as a
331 related metabolite of rosmarinic acid in human and animal plasma.^{31,32}

332

333 **Caco-2 cell transport experiments.**

334 Transport experiments of digested extracts were carried out using an *in vitro* model of
335 the intestinal barrier: Caco-2 cells differentiated to enterocytes³³. Prior to transport
336 experiments, the cytotoxicity of the digested extracts was evaluated at 6h. The results

337 showed that 150 μ L of the digested extracts was the maximum concentration that did
338 not significantly affected cell viability (data not shown). In addition, the integrity of the
339 Caco-2 monolayer during exposure experiments was evaluated as TEER-value.

340 Total phenolic compounds content recovered in apical and basolateral fractions for both
341 digested extracts was measured to determine the quantity of these compounds
342 unabsorbed and bioavailable, respectively (Table 4). For both extracts, only a small
343 amount of the phenolic compounds presented in the digested extracts was detected in
344 the bioavailable fraction. Thereby, the bioavailable fraction from enriched extract
345 presented a quantity of 84.8 mg GAE/L digested extract, meanwhile for original extract
346 only 68.5 mg GAE/L digested extract was detected in basolateral fraction.

347

348 The phenolic compounds recovered in apical and basolateral fractions for both digested
349 extracts were also analysed by HPLC in order to determine the bioavailability of
350 individual components (Table 5). The results indicated that, for both extracts, the main
351 component detected in basolateral fraction was RA, although enriched extract presented
352 a quantity 1.6 times superior. Besides RA, lithospermic acid isomer and diosmin were
353 the major components of basolateral fraction in both extracts, meanwhile 6-
354 hydroxyluteolin-7-O-glucoside and luteolin 7-O-glucoside, compounds with an
355 important presence after digestion process, only were presented in less than 5% in that
356 fraction.

357

358 The permeability of RA across Caco-2 cells monolayer has been studied by several
359 authors. Accordingly, Konishi and Kobayashi¹³ reported that RA transport throughout
360 Caco-2 cells was mainly *via* paracellular diffusion and its intestinal absorption
361 efficiency was low. These authors supported this idea with the fact that RA transport

362 increased linearly with the concentration and did not reach a plateau even at 30 nM.
363 However, more recently, Qiang et al.³⁴ suggested that RA was absorbed across Caco-2
364 cells *via* both paracellular and transcellular diffusion. Moreover, Falé et al.³⁵ reported
365 that the transport of RA across these cells was increased in presence of a mixture of
366 luteolin and apigenin, since these flavonoids may interfere in several mechanisms
367 involved in the permeation of RA, such as uptake and efflux mechanisms, indicating
368 that the flux of RA may be mediated by transport systems. Data obtained in this work
369 for RA were consistent with the idea that RA transport throughout Caco-2 cells was
370 mainly *via* paracellular diffusion, since in this case the transport increased linearly with
371 the concentration. Thus, enriched extract (after digestion) with a quantity of rosmarinic
372 acid 1.6 times higher than original extract, also presented in basolateral fraction 1.6 fold
373 of RA than original extract. However, it could not be discarded the influence of the
374 flavonoid content in the absorption efficiency of RA obtained in this work (approx.
375 14%).

376

377 In this work, the bioavailability of luteolin and apigenin derivatives was, in general,
378 lower than for RA, although, in this case the transport also increased linearly with the
379 concentration. However, in this study is noteworthy that, after 6h of experiment, the
380 amount of luteolin and apigenin aglycone in the apical compartment substantially
381 increased in relation to the amount of these components at t=0. According to those
382 results, Yasuda et al.³⁶ suggested that luteolin glucoside is partially hydrolysed by LPH
383 (lactase-phlorizin hydrolase), and moreover, only a fraction of the released aglycone is
384 absorbed inside the cells, where it is converted to its glucuronide conjugate, and
385 subsequently secreted to basolateral compartment. In this study, glucoside and
386 glucuronide forms of luteolin and apigenin were detected in basolateral solution after 6

387 h, inferring that a portion of glycoside derivatives are also transported in an unchanged
388 way across Caco-2 cells.^{37,38} Nevertheless, for a better comprehensive absorption path
389 for flavones, further analysis should be submitted.

390

391 In addition, antioxidant activity for both digested extracts was also measured in apical
392 and basolateral compartments and data are shown in Table 4. As could be observed, the
393 antioxidant activity detected in basolateral fraction from enriched extract was a ~~13%~~
394 significantly higher than that measured in this fraction when original extract was used.
395 This result was in agreement with the greater amount of phenolic compounds detected
396 in the basolateral chamber for this extract. Thus, mainly RA, lithospermic acid and
397 diosmin presented in the bioavailable fraction could be responsible of its antioxidant
398 activity.

399

400 **Anti-inflammatory activity of basolateral samples from Caco-2 experiments**

401 The activation of THP-1/M was carried out by LPS incorporation into the medium.
402 After 24h of incubation, LPS treated cells shown an important increase in all pro-
403 inflammatory cytokines measured (TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6), compared to non-activated
404 controls (Fig. 1). These activated cells were considered as positive controls for all the
405 cytokines tested. The cytotoxicity assays (data not shown) indicated that 20 μ L of the
406 basolateral fraction was the maximum concentration that did not affected THP-1
407 viability. Thus, when the activation of THP-1/M was carried out in presence of 20 μ L of
408 basolateral medium from Caco-2 experiments, an important decrease in TNF- α secreted
409 level was observed compared with levels obtained in absence of extracts (positive
410 control). Moreover, basolateral samples from enriched extract after digestion achieved
411 an 80% of inhibition in TNF- α secretion, higher to that obtained with the original

412 extract (40%). IL-1 β and IL-6 secretion were also reduced (60%) in presence of 20 μ L
413 basolateral fractions of original digested extracts (with respect to positive control). For
414 both interleukins, the enriched extract decreases its release in a greater extent than
415 original extract, a 70% for IL-1 β and an 85% for IL-6. Besides, the basolateral fraction
416 from control digestion did not reduced significantly the secretion of any of the pro-
417 inflammatory cytokines studied, compared to positive control.

418 Considering these results, basolateral fractions of both digested extracts presented an
419 important anti-inflammatory activity, although enriched extract showed a higher
420 inhibition in the release of all pro-inflammatory cytokines studied. In this regard,
421 several studies have reported that RA, either as pure standard or incorporated into a
422 vegetable matrix, inhibited LPS-induced up-regulation of IL-1 β , TNF- α and IL-6 in
423 different cells lines.^{11,12} Besides, luteolin and its derivatives have also been reported to
424 be able to inhibit the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as TNF- α and IL-
425 1 β .³⁹ However, none of these studies measured the inhibition in the production of these
426 cytokines by extracts or pure compounds after a digestion and absorption processes.

427 In conclusion, this study showed the potential use of marjoram extracts as a source of
428 bioavailable compounds with an important antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities.
429 Thus, the results indicated that PLE extracts from *Origanum majorana* L. represented a
430 rich source of bioavailable RA, especially when using the enriched extract. Besides RA,
431 luteolin derivatives, lithospermic acid isomer and diosmin were also detected in the
432 basolateral fraction in both extracts. Moreover, the bioavailable fractions of both
433 extracts showed a remarkable antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities, being more
434 prominent when using enriched extract. Thus, RA could have an important role in these
435 activities ~~could be mainly related with RA~~, although other phenolic compounds detected in

436 the basolateral fractions could also interact synergistically. ~~and with the presence of other~~
437 ~~phenolic compounds in a lesser extent.~~

438

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445

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614

Figure captions

Figure 1: Levels of TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6 secreted by THP-1/M, activated with LPS, in presence of bioavailable fractions from extracts. Positive control (cells stimulated with LPS but in absence of extract), negative control (cells in contact just with RPMI media), control digestion (bioavailable fraction from a digestion without extract, only digestion juices). Each bar is the mean of three determinations \pm S.D. * Denotes statistical differences when compares with positive control. ^{a,b,c} Different letters indicate statistical differences among original extract, enriched extract and digestion control. Significance level at $p \leq 0.05$ with LSD procedure.

Tables

Table 1. TPC content and antioxidant activity in original and enriched extracts.

		TPC (mg GAE/g)	TEAC value (mmol Trolox/g)
Original extract	initial	266 ± 4.80 ^{a₂}	1.81 ± 0.04 ^{a₂}
	after digestion	2220 ± 12.6 ^{b₂}	1.71 ± 0.05 ^{b₂}
Enriched extract	initial	389 ± 38.6 ^{a₁}	2.81 ± 0.01 ^{a₁}
	after digestion	312. ± 4.86 ^{b₁}	2.67 ± 0.03 ^{b₁}

Data shown represent means ± S.D. (n=3).

^{a,b} Different superscript letters denote significant differences within the same extract before and after digestion ($p \leq 0.05$).

^{1,2} Different subscript numbers denote significant differences between both extracts in the same condition (before or after digestion) ($p \leq 0.05$).

Table 2. Phenolic compounds identified in the samples using HPLC-PAD-MS/MS.

Peak	Compound	R _t (min)	λ _{max} (nm)	Acc. mass (m/z)	Error (ppm)	MS ² (m/z)
1	Neochlorogenic acid*	12.9	300, 326	353.0878	+1.3	191(100), 179(75), 135(30)
2	Protocatechuic acid*	13.4	260, 294	153.0193	+1.2	153(30), 109(100)
3	Caftaric acid*	13.7	300, 328	311.0408	+2.5	149(100)
4	Cryptochlorogenic acid*	15.1	300, 326	353.0878	+4.0	191(100), 179(75), 135(30)
5	Vicenin II*	15.9	272, 336	593.1511	-1.8	503(20), 473(100), 383(20), 353(30)
6	Caffeic acid*	17.8	299, 324	179.0349	+2.6	135(100)
7	6-hydroxyluteolin-7-O-glucoside	19.8	282, 344	463.0882	-4.1	463 (20), 301(100)
8	p-coumaric*	22.9	310	163.0400	+2.1	119(100)
9	Luteolin-O-glucoside	23.4	282, 334	447.0932	-3.4	285(100), 151(20)
10	Luteolin 7-O-glucoside*	23.8	254, 266, 348	447.0932	-2.6	285(100), 151(20)
11	Luteolin 7-O-glucuronide*	24.0	254, 266, 348	461.0725	-4.7	285(100), 151(20)
12	Diosmin*	27.1	352, 266, 346	607.1668	-2.7	607(10), 299(100), 284(10)
13	Apigenin 7-O-glucoside*	27.6	266, 336	431.0983	-4.6	431(20), 269(100)
14	Apigenin 7-O-glucuronide*	28.1	266, 336	445.0776	-4.3	445(20), 269(100)
15	Rosmarinic acid*	28.9	288, 330	359.0772	+0.7	197(20), 161(100), 179(30), 135(20)
16	Lithospermic acid	29.7	288, 310, 334	537.1038	-4.9	493(10), 359(30), 295(30), 197(20), 161(100), 135(80)

	isomer					
17	Salvianolic acid isomer	30.4	288, 310, 334	717.1461	-2.8	717(10), 519(30), 475(10), 359(100), 295(10), 179(10)
18	Luteolin*	33.7	254, 266, 348	285.0404	-3.0	285(20), 217(35), 175(100), 151(50)
19	Apigenin*	37.0	266, 336	269.0444	-3.8	269(20), 225(30), 151(100), 119(50)

616 *Comparison with standards

617 .

Table 3. Effect of *in vitro* gastrointestinal digestion process in extracts composition.

Compound	Original extract (mg/g extract)		Enriched extract (mg/g extract)	
	Initial	After digestion	Initial	After digestion
Neochlorogenic acid	N.D. ^b	0.57 ± 0.01 *	N.D.	0.88 ± 0.02 *
Protocatechuic acid	0.17 ± 0.01	0.19 ± 0.00 *	0.30 ± 0.01	0.18 ± 0.00 *
Caftaric acid	0.06 ± 0.00	0.04 ± 0.00 *	0.10 ± 0.01	0.09 ± 0.00
Cryptochlorogenic acid	0.86 ± 0.00	0.53 ± 0.00 *	1.49 ± 0.01	0.76 ± 0.00 *
Vicenin II	2.32 ± 0.02	2.24 ± 0.03 *	4.00 ± 0.01	3.73 ± 0.01 *
Caffeic acid	0.93 ± 0.07	0.57 ± 0.01 *	1.32 ± 0.01	0.88 ± 0.01 *
6-hydroxyluteolin-7-O-glucoside	33.9 ± 0.09	14.5 ± 0.18 *	60.9 ± 0.04	21.0 ± 0.23 *
p-coumaric	N.D.	0.36 ± 0.00 *	N.D.	0.52 ± 0.00 *
Luteolin-O-glucoside	25.2 ± 0.03	10.5 ± 0.12 *	44.7 ± 0.02	15.3 ± 0.17 *
Luteolin 7-O-glucoside	15.5 ± 0.08	14.6 ± 0.02 *	25.5 ± 0.01	21.8 ± 0.04 *
Luteolin 7-O-glucuronide	5.69 ± 0.02	5.38 ± 0.02 *	9.29 ± 0.01	8.17 ± 0.04 *
Diosmin	6.48 ± 0.04	6.46 ± 0.03	10.3 ± 0.01	10.8 ± 0.06 *
Apigenin 7-O-glucoside	2.45 ± 0.02	3.22 ± 0.03 *	4.69 ± 0.01	4.90 ± 0.04 *
Apigenin 7-O-glucuronide	3.64 ± 0.49	5.74 ± 0.06 *	7.20 ± 0.01	8.70 ± 0.02 *
Rosmarinic acid	33.9 ± 0.05	19.0 ± 0.11 *	57.2 ± 0.05	29.0 ± 0.34 *
Lithospermic acid isomer	9.10 ± 0.02	6.91 ± 0.11 *	15.9 ± 0.05	11.0 ± 0.11 *
Salvianolic acid isomer	17.2 ± 0.35	2.60 ± 0.14 *	24.9 ± 0.16	4.27 ± 0.09 *
Luteolin	1.39 ± 0.08	0.55 ± 0.03 *	2.07 ± 0.01	0.73 ± 0.02 *
Apigenin	0.45 ± 0.01	0.22 ± 0.00 *	0.75 ± 0.01	0.31 ± 0.04 *

^aN.D. = non detected. * Denotes significant difference when compares initial and after digestion concentration within same extract ($p \leq 0.05$). Data represent means \pm S.D. (n=4).

Table 4. TPC content and antioxidant activity in original and enriched extracts after caco-2 absorption experiments.

		TPC (mg GAE/L digested extract)	TEAC value (mmol Trolox/L digested extract)
Original extract	After digestion	502 ± 18.1 ^{a₂}	3.41 ± 0.16 ^{a₂}
	Apical fraction	358 ± 26.7 ^{b₂}	1.77 ± 0.21 ^{b₂}
	Basolateral fraction	68.5 ± 6.40 ^{c₂}	0.73 ± 0.01 ^{c₂}
Enriched extract	After digestion	684 ± 31.1 ^{a₁}	4.78 ± 0.58 ^{a₁}
	Apical fraction	556 ± 40.5 ^{b₁}	3.74 ± 0.36 ^{b₁}
	Basolateral fraction	84.8 ± 7.86 ^{c₁}	0.89 ± 0.09 ^{c₁}

Data shown represent means ± S.D. (n=3).

^{a,b,c} Different superscript letters denote significant differences within the different fractions of the same extract ($p \leq 0.05$).

^{1,2} Different subscript numbers denote significant differences among the same fractions of both extracts ($p \leq 0.05$).

Table 5. Extracts phenolic composition after caco-2 absorption experiments.

Compound	Original extract (mg/L digested extract)			Enriched extract (mg/L digested extract)		
	Initial	Apical	Basolateral	Initial	Apical	Basolateral
Neochlorogenic acid	1.45 ± 0.41	0.94 ± 0.04	0.31 ± 0.03	2.09 ± 0.03	1.77 ± 0.09	0.41 ± 0.07
Protocatechuic acid	0.45 ± 0.03	0.37 ± 0.00	N.D. ^b	0.43 ± 0.03	0.39 ± 0.04	N.D.
Caftaric acid	0.06 ± 0.00	N.D.	N.D.	0.15 ± 0.03	0.05 ± 0.00	N.D.
Cryptochlorogenic acid	1.27 ± 0.00	0.81 ± 0.08	0.13 ± 0.03	1.75 ± 0.02	1.39 ± 0.09	0.21 ± 0.07
Vicenin II	4.81 ± 0.54	4.07 ± 0.52	0.63 ± 0.09	8.35 ± 0.14	7.74 ± 0.42	1.00 ± 0.40
Caffeic acid	1.51 ± 0.17	1.08 ± 0.10	0.37 ± 0.03	2.39 ± 0.01	1.86 ± 0.07	0.54 ± 0.09
6-hydroxyluteolin-7-O-glucoside	17.1 ± 1.04	2.66 ± 0.35	0.47 ± 0.29	20.5 ± 0.43	6.69 ± 1.09	1.01 ± 0.62
p-coumaric	0.80 ± 0.15	0.50 ± 0.03	0.30 ± 0.01	1.38 ± 0.05	0.81 ± 0.01	0.45 ± 0.06
Luteolin-O-glucoside	12.8 ± 0.84	2.81 ± 0.10	0.42 ± 0.21	15.9 ± 0.41	6.61 ± 0.89	1.02 ± 0.58
Luteolin 7-O-glucoside	17.2 ± 1.35	2.69 ± 0.41	0.54 ± 0.32	23.84 ± 0.58	8.34 ± 1.22	1.03 ± 0.05
Luteolin 7-O-glucuronide	7.03 ± 0.99	2.26 ± 0.04	0.74 ± 0.06	8.36 ± 0.23	4.71 ± 0.28	1.26 ± 0.03
Diosmin	10.5 ± 0.19	8.56 ± 0.02	1.06 ± 0.21	15.7 ± 0.17	18.6 ± 1.36	1.96 ± 0.62
Apigenin 7-O-glucoside	4.25 ± 0.10	1.66 ± 0.02	0.17 ± 0.06	6.20 ± 0.08	3.72 ± 0.14	0.46 ± 0.21
Apigenin 7-O-glucuronide	9.03 ± 0.36	3.23 ± 0.38	0.75 ± 0.16	13.4 ± 0.24	7.33 ± 0.19	1.40 ± 0.47
Rosmarinic acid	32.2 ± 2.30	23.1 ± 4.05	4.45 ± 0.54	51.6 ± 2.61	42.4 ± 5.63	7.37 ± 1.39
Lithospermic acid isomer	11.4 ± 1.02	8.53 ± 1.37	1.45 ± 0.29	18.3 ± 0.76	14.4 ± 0.08	2.13 ± 0.42
Salvianolic acid isomer	4.27 ± 0.41	3.20 ± 0.33	0.61 ± 0.08	6.44 ± 0.10	4.82 ± 0.10	0.87 ± 0.10
Luteolin	0.23 ± 0.02	1.92 ± 0.75	0.15 ± 0.01	0.45 ± 0.00	3.82 ± 0.69	0.61 ± 0.47
Apigenin	0.04 ± 0.00	0.70 ± 0.39	N.D.	0.07 ± 0.00	1.48 ± 0.37	0.17 ± 0.00

^a Data represent means ± S.D. (n= 4). ^b N.D. = non detected.

Figures

Figure 1

Graphics

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